

Residential Migration from the Core to the Periphery of Tirana: Emerging Trends and Patterns

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Abstract

Migratory movements in Albania have a long history, shaped by the country's political, economic, and social conditions. These movements are primarily characterized by internal migration, which has significantly influenced territorial transformations, demographic changes, and the organization of economic and social life. The largest cities in Albania, particularly Tirana, have been the most affected. Tirana, which has undergone profound transformation since becoming the capital in 1920, is a prime example of internal migration. The city has seen a significant influx of individuals from other regions of the country seeking to establish residence there. The drivers of migration to Tirana are tied to geographical, economic, and social factors. Consequently, the socio-economic effects of this migration have reshaped the city in numerous ways.

After the 1990s, the primary migration patterns in Albania shifted from small towns to large cities and from rural areas to urban centers. Recently, however, a new trend has emerged, with movements from urban areas back to rural regions, particularly noticeable in the country's capital. The geography of residential migration is characterized by a population decline in six urban units of the Municipality of Tirana, while population growth is more pronounced in four specific rural units, with positive trends in most rural areas. These population shifts have created an urgent need to implement territorial development policies in both urban and rural areas of the Municipality of Tirana.

Keywords

residential migration, rural areas, counter – urbanization, population shifts, demographic changes, primate city, urban growth

JEL codes: J11, J60, O15, O18, O20, R10

Introduction

The patterns of internal migration have evolved over time, reflecting broader socio-economic transformations. In the latter half of the 20th century, urbanization was a dominant trend, with large numbers of people moving from rural to urban areas in search of better employment opportunities and living conditions (Todaro 1969). This rural-to-urban migration has been particularly pronounced in developing countries, contributing to the rapid growth of megacities (Cohen 2006). These movements are primarily associated with residential migration and have had a significant impact on territorial transformation, demographic changes, and the organization of economic and social life. More recently, a countertrend has emerged, characterized by urban-to-rural migration, often driven by lifestyle preferences and telecommuting opportunities (Halfacree 2008). This phenomenon, sometimes referred to as “counter-urbanization,” has been observed in various countries, including the United States and parts of Europe (Champion 1989). Similar trends have also been noted in Balkan countries.

In recent years, migration movement from major cities like Belgrade, Tirana, and Skopje have increasingly shifted toward suburban areas, driven by the pursuit of better living standards, reduced expenses, and an enhanced quality of life. In Tirana, as the primate city of Albania, urbanization has traditionally driven population movements, with rural inhabitants flocking to cities in search of better employment opportunities, education, and services. The history of migration in Albania dates back to ancient times. In terms of external migration, since 1405, the population has chosen to move southward toward Greece, while internal migration remained more stable during this period (Islami 1994). In Albania, migratory movements are studied across three distinct periods, each reflecting the country’s political, economic, and social conditions. The first period encompasses migration before 1945, the second spans from 1945 to 1990, and the third covers the decades from 1990 to the present day.

Before 1945, Albanian migration was shaped by conquests, war conflicts, economic factors, and state policies. During the Ottoman occupation of Albania, particularly between the 15th and 17th centuries, a significant number of Albanians emigrated to Italy (notably to Calabria and Sicily), Dalmatia, and Greece. Those migratory movements led to the formation of Arbëresh communities in Italy. Meanwhile, in the interwar period, migration trends were predominantly directed toward the United States, Canada, and Western European countries, closely tied to the economic conditions of the destination nations. In the second period (1945-1990), the establishment of the communist regime led to the prohibition of emigration, and internal migration was tightly controlled (IN-STAT 2001). When discussing residential migration, this period was marked by deliberate movements of the population within the country. Sjöberg argues that despite policies aimed at controlling migration, one-third of the population was involved in internal migration. However, Sjöberg also proposes the zero urban growth hypothesis, suggesting that urban growth rates will eventually approach zero as urbanization stabilizes and reaches its peak. This hypothesis posits that cities will eventually reach a state of equilibrium in terms of population and spatial expansion (Sjöberg 1992). While Sjöberg’s zero urban growth hypothesis provides a useful framework for understanding potential long-term trends in urbanization, it is important to consider the diverse and dynamic factors that influence urban growth, which can vary significantly across different contexts and time periods.

The data on internal migration in Albania primarily pertains to displacements from rural areas to urban centers. The most intensive migration was recorded in the Tirana – Durrës – Elbasan triangle (King & Vullnetari 2003). The significant urban growth rate of 7% during the 1950s was driven by migratory movements, which were twice the rate of the population's natural growth. This rural-to-urban migration significantly accelerated the rate of urbanization. The urban population doubled within a decade, reaching 31% of the country's total population (Lerch 2014).

During the period from 1945 to 1990, as in all former socialist states, the change of political regime was accompanied by social and demographic transformations (Darques 2004). For the first time since the beginning of the century, the population decreased, dropping from 3.182.000 to 3.087.000 inhabitants. According to data, Albania lost nearly 3% of its residents between 1989 and 2001 (Darques 2004). Nearly 23% of the Albanian population left the country in just over a decade. However, between 1989 and 2001, the regions of Tirana and Durrës attracted 100,000 new residents. During the intercensal period of 2001–2011, it is estimated that approximately 500.000 individuals emigrated from Albania, averaging around 50.000 people per year. This emigration trend has remained nearly constant, with an annual average of 50,000 emigrants. Meanwhile, according to IN-STAT data (2023), the total population of Albania declined from 2.8 million to 2.4 million inhabitants. Thus, with a decline in the total population by about 14%. In all districts, except for Tirana, the population has been declining during the period from 2011 to 2023. The population of the Tirana district has increased by 1.2%, mostly due to internal migration. The population growth in Tirana and the decline in other districts have resulted in an increase in the percentage of the population residing in Tirana, from 26.8% in 2011 to 31.6% in 2023 (INSTAT 2023). The peri-urban countryside has seen notable migration, with its original inhabitants moving to the cities, being replaced by individuals from more distant regions.

The urban population growth rate in the 1990s was just 1.1%, exactly the same as the natural growth rate. In urban areas, natural growth was considered a significant factor, which can be attributed to the stable level of urban growth and the migratory movements oriented towards countries beyond Albania's borders (Lerch 2014). The geographic concentration of internal migration did not change significantly compared to the 1990s, with Tirana and Durrës remaining the primary destinations. During the 2000s, over half of internal migrants were directed to these areas, a trend that was stronger than the pattern of immigration. Thus, internal migration in the 2000s continued to reflect a movement from peripheral areas to cities, although many individuals also settled in suburban areas.

Combined with return migration this trend contributed to a rapid increase in urbanization, with more than 50% of the population living in formal urban areas by 2011, up from 36% in 1989 (INSTAT 2014b). The 2011 Census confirmed a continuing trend of emigration, particularly from rural areas, which were losing approximately 2.6% of their population annually. Meanwhile, the urban population continued to grow at an annual rate of 1.2%, driven primarily by emigration and internal rural migration (IN-STAT 2014a). The share of the urban population in Albania remained relatively stable at around 62.97% in 2021. However, this percentage was the highest recorded during the observed period (STATISTA 2021). At the national level, these migratory trends remain dominant even today. Figure 1 visually presents the trend of population movement towards urban areas.

Figure 1. Urban and rural population in Albania from 1950 to 2050. *Source:* [United Nations, 2018]

According to the World Urbanization Prospects, the settlement structure of the Albanian population is expected to maintain current trends, with most of the population continuing to reside in urban areas. By 2035, the population living in urban areas is predicted to represent over 70% of the country's total population (UN 2018). This underscores the crucial role played by major urban centers in Albania, highlighting the characteristics of the center – periphery model. This model is characterized by the dominance of the urban population, high population density in central areas, and the increasing establishment of economic and social activities in the suburbs.

Methodology

This paper employs a comprehensive methodology to explore the growing trend of rural migration in Tirana, incorporating fourteen in-depth interviews, cartography, and comparative analysis. The in-depth interviews provide qualitative insights by capturing the personal motivations and experiences of individuals who have relocated from urban to rural areas. This approach aims to uncover the personal challenges and experiences associated with the migration process. Cartography is used to create a detailed map that visualizes net migration in the municipality of Tirana from 2010 to 2020. This map highlights areas with significant population changes, offering a clear geographical representation of migration trends. The cartographic analysis utilizes data sourced from INSTAT and municipal records, processed using Geographic Information System (GIS) software. This visual representation aids in understanding the spatial dynamics of migration and identifies specific rural areas attracting urban residents.

A comparative analysis was also conducted to examine differences in migration patterns over various time periods within the decade under study. This involved comparing migration rates and factors influencing migration at different intervals. Together, these methodologies provide a holistic view of migration trends by integrating personal narratives with spatial and temporal data.

Results and discussions

The trend of residential migration from urban to rural areas has been accelerating, driven by broader social, economic, and environmental changes. This shift is particularly evident in Tirana, the city that holds primary importance in Albania. Historically, the population tends to settle in those geographical areas where it is attracted by better job prospects, educational opportunities, and services. However, current trends reveal a reversal, with an increasing number of urban dwellers opting to move to rural regions.

The geography of residential migration in Tirana municipality

Tirana is a city that has undergone significant metamorphosis in terms of urbanization and spatial organization. As the capital of the country, it has experienced the most significant territorial changes compared to other cities. Under these conditions, Tirana serves as a representative example of residential migration due to the high demand from the population to move to this urban area. The selection of Tirana as the capital in 1920 marked the beginning of its urban expansion. The new capital benefited from organizational efforts initiated by King Zog. Its population grew from 25,000 inhabitants in 1938 to 60,000 in 1945. Between 1945 and 1989, Tirana's urban population quadrupled, increasing from 60,000 to 240,000 residents. Residential migration patterns have changed significantly in recent decades. The motives behind migratory movements in the Tirana area are related to immigrants' hopes for better quality in education, health, social support, and more employment opportunities. For those moving from the northern mountainous areas of the country to Tirana, poor living conditions and limited opportunities are significant factors driving their relocation to urban or suburban areas.

After 1990, migration occurred in two main directions: from rural areas to urban areas, and from small towns to larger cities, particularly Tirana. In 1997, the registered population in the Municipality of Tirana was 568,758, representing 18% of the country's total population (Çabiri et al. 1998). The lack of development plans for the city, combined with these migratory movements, led to a rapid and chaotic expansion. Tirana, which covered an area of 15.4 km² in 1985, expanded to 41.8 km² by the late 1990s (Koka 2008).

According to INSTAT (2014a), between 2001 and 2011, the number of urban agglomerations in Albania decreased from 17 to 13. Population growth was observed only in the agglomerations of Tirana, Durrës, Lezha, and Saranda. During this period, Tirana experienced significant urban expansion, with a growth rate of +15.8%, followed by the suburbs of the metropolitan area (Tirana – Durrës). Additionally, INSTAT (2020) reported a 31.8% increase in the number of building permits in the region of Tirana between 2016 and 2018, with similar increases observed in the regions of Durrës and Fier. Overall, the density of the resident population in the center has increased, and interactions between the urban and suburban areas of the Municipality of Tirana have become more intense, partly due to daily movements for work or study.

Examining the evolution of population and density over the years, we see that the Municipality of Tirana has never experienced a decline in these indicators. According to data from the Civil Registry of the Municipality of Tirana, the population reached 867,890 in 2022, up from 761,020 in 2013. This population increase has led to a rise in population density, with an average annual growth rate of 12 inhabitants per km². In 2021, the population density was 777 inhabitants per km², compared to 685 inhabitants per km² in 2013, according

to the General Directorate of Civil Status of the Municipality of Tirana (2019). These outcomes primarily stem from population migration trends, which are evident in the stability of increasing population numbers contrasted with natural growth. The balance of migratory movements – calculated as the difference between new registrations and de-registrations – showed dynamic fluctuations between 2010 and 2020. This dynamism is observed in both the urban and rural areas of the Tirana municipality.

Among the 11 urban units, population displacement is more pronounced in 6 of them. Similarly, out of the 13 rural units within the Tirana Municipality, a notable population influx is observed in 4 units, while the balance of movements is lower in the remaining units, with some experiencing population outflows. The geography of residential migration is characterized by a significant departure from urban units No. 1, No. 4, No. 6, No. 8, No. 10, and No. 11. In contrast, the arrival of the population is more pronounced in rural units such as Dajt, Farkë, Kashar, and Vaqarr. Additionally, population trends show increases in Bërzhitë, Pezë, and Zall-Herr, whereas units like Baldushk, Ndroq, Petrelë, Shëngjergj, and Zall-Bastar experience population declines.

According to the data from the Civil Registry of Tirana Municipality, the difference between registrations and de-registrations, reflecting movements from first to second residences, peaked in 2017 with 17,452 residents. Despite minor declines between 2014 and 2016, the balance of migratory movements generally maintained positive trends. However, in 2020, this balance was half of what it was in 2019, likely due to the impact of the pandemic. These trends raise questions about the validity of United Nations hypotheses regarding continuous urban population growth in Albania. *Will residential migration from urban to rural areas be able to curb the dominance of the urban population in the future?* Addressing these trends will require intervention from government actors through comprehensive development plans for both rural and urban areas. Figure 2 visualizes the net migration movements in the municipality of Tirana from 2010 to 2020.

The map illustrates that residential migration within the Municipality of Tirana is significantly influenced by distance from the city center, following a center – periphery pattern. Data shows that the most substantial population movements occur in rural units closer to the city center, where people tend to relocate. In contrast, rural units located on the outskirts of the Municipality, where distances from the center are greater, experience a tendency for the population to leave. Official data and map illustrations reveal that new residents moving from urban areas of Tirana to its outskirts primarily prefer settling in the southern and southeastern parts of the capital, with some also moving towards the west. Despite their desire to escape the environmental pollution and congestion of public spaces in the city, these residents generally do not move far from the services offered by the urban area.

The three most preferred rural zones for relocation are Farka, Dajti, and Kashar. These areas are favored for their proximity to the city center and their accessibility due to existing physical infrastructure. Despite having a higher cost of living compared to other rural areas of Tirana, these zones remain popular. The increasing demand for relocation to the outskirts, driven by both local and foreign residents (mainly Italians), has led to a reassessment of land and building prices even in the more distant suburbs of Tirana. It is observed that homes in these areas often feature construction styles and interior conditions conducive to an urban lifestyle. Although residents are moving to rural spaces, they tend not to adopt local architectural styles but prefer to live in low-rise and high-rise developments (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Net migration of population in the Municipality of Tirana during 2010-2020. *Note:* The map illustrates the net migration of urban and rural areas within the municipality of Tirana (blue color: negative evolution; red color: positive evolution). Administrative Units 1 to 11 represent the urban areas, while the other units represent the rural ones. *Source:* [UMR Territoire, 2020].

Figure 3. Models of residences in the peripheral areas of Tirana. *Source:* photos by the authors

The photos illustrate the current reality of Tirana's peripheral areas. Despite being labeled as peripheral, these areas are beginning to show signs of urbanization. If population and economic activities continue to shift towards these regions, the concept of "periphery" may extend to even more distant territories within the municipality of Tirana.

Motives of residential migration and new movement trends in the city of Tirana

Residential mobility is influenced by the costs associated with moving and the anticipated benefits individuals expect to gain from relocating. A notable trend in internal migration is the movement from the city of Tirana to its suburban areas. This trend has become increasingly prominent in recent years. We observe a spreading of the population from the city center, emerging industrialization in the suburban areas of Tirana, and a redistribution or mixing of economic activities, in contrast to other cities in Albania (INSTAT 2014a).

The socio-economic impacts of residential migration are profound. Urban areas experiencing high inflows of migrants often undergo significant demographic changes, leading to increased demand for housing, infrastructure, and services (Sassen 2001). This can result in both positive outcomes, such as economic growth and cultural diversity, and negative consequences, such as urban sprawl and social inequality (Florida 2002). Residential migration is driven by a variety of factors that can vary significantly depending on individual circumstances, economic conditions, and societal influences. People often move in search of better job prospects, higher wages, or lower living costs, seeking improved living conditions including access to healthcare, education, public services, and recreational facilities. These reasons are particularly relevant to the migratory movements of the population in Tirana, as many residents relocate toward the city's periphery.

To understand the current situation, fourteen in-depth interviews were conducted with young residents of Tirana's outskirts. Some interviewees have a complex history of residential movements, having initially migrated from northern or southern cities of Albania to the center of Tirana. Today, many of these individuals prefer relocating from the center of Tirana to its suburbs. There are also numerous cases, 9 from 14, where this shift has occurred without a prior history of migration, with people moving directly from the urban center of Tirana to its outskirts. The reasons for settling in Tirana's suburban areas are varied, including factors such as quality of life, psychological well-being, cultural opportunities, health, access to public spaces, connection with nature, and lower living costs. The interviewees' preference for remaining in the outskirts, despite the challenges, indicates a strong desire for these benefits. This trend exemplifies the broader movement of urban-to-rural migration driven by a quest for improved quality of life, while also highlighting the ongoing need for rural development to better support these residents.

Given the recent trends in migratory movements, it is crucial for government actors to implement territorial, economic, and social policies aimed at managing the development of rural areas and decentralizing the city center. Rural areas experiencing depopulation may face challenges such as declining economies, reduced public services, and aging populations (Johnson 2006). However, the influx of urban-to-rural migrants can revitalize these areas by bringing in new economic activities and investments (Stockdale 2016).

In the Municipality of Tirana, key actors are focusing on enhancing cohesion between the city center and its periphery. These migratory movements, oriented from the center towards rural areas, which are increasingly growing day by day, are contributing to the urbanization

of these rural spaces. This may potentially lead to the transformation of these rural areas into suburban zones in the future. On the other hand, the local General Plan (General local plan of Tirana Municipality, 2017) recognizes the need to propose new functions and the redevelopment of former industrial areas in urban and peri-urban areas. This strategy aims to gradually relocate heavy manufacturing activities away from main business routes to facilitate the growth of economic, recreational, and tourist activities. Effective policy responses are essential to managing the challenges and opportunities associated with residential migration (Glaeser & Gyourko 2018). Proactive and thoughtful government actions can help manage migration dynamics in ways that benefit both migrants and host communities while minimizing potential negative impacts.

Conclusion

Residential migration is a dynamic process with significant implications for both urban and rural areas. Understanding the trends, drivers, and impacts of migration is essential for policymakers, urban planners, and researchers. The historical evolution of population migration in Albania can be divided into three distinct periods shaped by political circumstances. Before 1945, Albania experienced significant emigration to neighboring countries due to internal political, economic, and social challenges. From 1945 to 1990, migration within and outside Albania was strictly regulated by the communist regime, which controlled and directed population movements according to state policies. From the 1990s to the present day, migration trends have shifted towards uncontrolled movements. This period has been primarily characterized by residential migration, with individuals moving in search of improved quality of life and economic opportunities. Tirana has historically been profoundly affected by these migratory movements, particularly since the 1990s when the Tirana – Durrës region attracted 35% of the population's immigration. This influx from rural areas has significantly boosted the region's urbanization rate, necessitating a reorganization of both urban and rural units within the municipality. Over the past decade, there has been a noticeable trend of population preference shifting from the city center towards its suburbs. This is evident from the population departures in many urban units and their resettlement in rural areas closer to Tirana's core.

Based on the processed data, the cartographic analysis reveals that migration within Tirana follows a center – periphery pattern. Significant movement is observed towards rural units closer to the city center, while outflows occur from units farther away. The interviews highlight several motives for residential migration, including quality of life factors, psychological well-being, cultural opportunities, health, access to public spaces, connection with nature, and lower living costs. Emerging trends in residential migration and the relocation of economic activities are driving new territorial developments. In the Municipality of Tirana, the city center exerts a strong influence on its peripheries. This influence is particularly pronounced in areas closer to the center, which in turn fosters complementary relationships among surrounding rural areas.

Territorial plans propose redeveloping former industrial areas to foster economic, recreational, and tourist activities while gradually relocating heavy manufacturing from urban cores. However, residential migration within the Municipality of Tirana is driving new territorial developments. The shift of residences and economic activities from the city center to its outskirts necessitates a reconfiguration of Tirana's spatial layout. Despite these no-

ticeable trends, migration is unfolding gradually, as Tirana continues to retain primary functions that are not easily replaced by rural areas within the municipality. This context raises important questions about whether this migration is merely a passing trend or the beginning of a sustained movement. Will the intensity of migration continue at its current pace? How can we effectively manage the expansion of urbanization into rural territories? While residential migration in Tirana is still in its early stages, sustained intervention by decision-makers will likely be necessary if this trend continues. Effective management of territorial space will be crucial to accommodate these changes and ensure balanced development.

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